

Introduction

A non-fungible token (NFT) is a digital asset with a unique identity, representing a piece of a digital object, art or media. It is secured on a blockchain, a decentralized ledger that records ownership and provenance, ensuring its authenticity and scarcity. The inherent contradictions and versatile nature of NFTs are what make this phenomenon a fertile ground for further investigation. While they ostensibly provide a decentralized platform for artists to interact directly with their audiences, bypassing traditional gatekeepers, the reality is that NFTs, like other contemporary art forms, are often subject to the same market forces and institutional constraints. This feature positions them within the ongoing dialectical discussion of art's utopian potential, a potential that is inevitably intertwined with dystopian realities.

NFTs have elicited both enthusiasm and criticism. They are associated with the capacity for rapid financial gain or loss through the creation and trading of digital images. They also depend on the global geopolitical situation, which is clearly visible after the recent US elections. It is the end of 2024. One of the first NFTs, CryptoPunks, was launched in 2017. More notable early examples of NFTs include *The First 5,000 Days* by Beeple or Bored Ape Yacht Club, which were very good collectible investments. Nevertheless, the emergence of new technologies invariably stimulates artists to critically examine and redefine the commercialization of art. This approach is exemplified by the work of artists like Fred Forest, Kevin Abosch, Damien Hirst, Marina Abramović, and others. This unique economic context gives rise to a characteristic aesthetic, often manifested in commercial projects as 8-bit graphics and in conceptual ones as the critical dimensions of the artwork.

As a novel actant within the realm of digital cultures, NFTs fulfil a multitude of functions, including social, aesthetic, economic, ludic, and even charitable purposes. Formally, they can serve as both a medium and a message, a substance and a distribution platform. They have emerged as one of the most hotly debated phenomena in new media art, polarizing public opinion and artists alike. This polarization is often characterized by a tension between concerns about environmental impact and the potential for significant artistic autonomy beyond financial considerations.

Thus, several questions arise when contemplating NFTs as a new digital art phenomenon. The following topics are proposed for discussion: peer-to-peer

technology, a utopia of creative freedom, and a crypto-capitalist delusion. Moreover, it's the aesthetic and economic values of blockchain-based art, media archaeology, new colonialism in blockchain-minted art, technology and its energy-intensive nature, as well as the impact of blockchain on climate changes, portals as collectors and taste experts, and many other issues.

This volume brings together a diverse range of texts that explore topics such as the definition and nature of crypto art (Polish translation of Domenico Quaranta's text), the question of NFTs as a medium in art (Ryszard W. Kluszczyński), the potential of blockchain for alternative economy and ecology (Małgorzata Dancewicz-Pawlik), and the intersection of art and technology through the lens of Fluxus from an autoethnographic perspective (Georg Eckmayr). It further delves into ontological questions (Bogna J. Gladden-Obidzińska), the implications of cellular automata for digital societies (Dagmara Domagała), and the potential of NFTs to reshape African art markets, with a particular focus on Kenya (Anne Mwiti).

A significant challenge also lies in the time lag between writing about rapidly evolving technologies and their eventual publication. Consequently, this raises the question of the printed publications' role as a more enduring form of documentation compared to digital content, which is subject to the volatility of servers and domains. Since I think that locating research in a particular place and moment helps in historicizing art and technology, I also see this volume as a kind of documentation of where we were at the turn of the years 2024 and 2025.

The issues related to NFTs raised in this volume generate more questions than answers. This, in a sense, highlights my initial belief when embarking on this project: that the phenomenon of blockchain-based art is still in its formative stages, marking the commencement of a discourse on the hybrid phenomena of entities, objects, and events of fluxual character. While I emphasize the dialectical nature of this occurrence, it is important to note that this ambivalent character is only apparent at first glance. This is a deeply hybrid phenomenon. The volume is intended to stimulate curiosity and critical thinking, and to set the stage for future discussions.

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